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THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET AND THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN IT

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Abstract: This article discusses the development of the metallurgical industry in the region, which will increase the demand for metal products used in construction, transport, energy and other sectors, and will benefit small businesses operating in the Tashkent region. The activities of small businesses in various sectors of the regional economy, including the production, sale and processing of metal products, were considered.

Key words: Business, market, construction, transport, energy, metal products.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada qurilish, transport, energetika va boshqa sohalarda qo'llaniladigan metall mahsulotlariga bo'lgan talabni oshirish hamda Toshkent viloyatida faoliyat yuritayotgan kichik biznes sub'yektlariga foyda keltiruvchi hududda metallurgiya sanoatini rivojlantirish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Viloyat iqtisodiyotining turli tarmoqlarida, jumladan, metall buyumlar ishlab chiqarish, sotish va qayta ishlashda kichik biznes subyektlarining faoliyati ko'rib chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Biznes, bozor, qurilish, transport, energetika, metall buyumlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается развитие металлургической промышленности региона, что будет способствовать росту спроса на металлопродукцию, используемую в строительстве, транспорте, энергетике и других отраслях, а также принесет пользу малому бизнесу, работающему в Ташкентской области. Рассмотрена деятельность малого бизнеса в различных секторах экономики региона, включая производство, реализацию и переработку металлопродукции.

Ключевые слова: Бизнес, рынок, строительство, транспорт, энергетика, металлопродукция.

INTRODUCTION

The development of ferrous metallurgy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the most important priority state task of the modern stage of economic development. Continuous reconstruction, technical re-equipment and modernization of production allows us to produce high-quality competitive products, which supply products to industrial enterprises and the construction industry of the republic, as well as export.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Program for the Development of the Joint-Stock Company "Uzmetkombinat" dated December 28, 2020 No. PQ-4937 "On Measures for the Implementation of the Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2023", a large investment project "Construction of a Casting and Rolling Complex" is being implemented by the Joint-Stock Company "Uzmetkombinat". The project implementation period is 2020-2024. The "Construction of a Casting and Rolling Complex" project is the largest investment project. Based on this project, the plant will produce 1.04 million tons of import-substituting, export-oriented, hot-rolled steel sheet coils. As a result of the implementation of this project, the plant's production capacity will almost double. "Daniel" (Italy), a world leader in the supply of metallurgical equipment company and the contractor «Ronesanc Austria» (Turkey), which has extensive international experience in the construction of industrial facilities, are cooperating in the implementation of this investment project. Currently, the construction of the Casting and Rolling Complex is in full swing.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert RGIbragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development

and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aecker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others..

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results

The main macroeconomic indicators of the Tashkent region have been showing positive growth rates for years. This can be observed in the indicators of GRP, industry, agriculture, and foreign trade.

Table 1. Economic Growth Indicators of the Tashkent Region (2015–2025)

Year	GRP	Industry	Construction	Employment
2015	64.8	30.8	70.7	76.8
2016	66.2	34.0	73.8	76.9
2017	63.3	30.0	77.2	75.1
2018	57.3	28.9	75.1	73.2
2019	49.8	22.1	79.6	72.8
2020	49.2	22.3	80.8	70.8
2021	46.8	17.3	76.4	69.8
2022	46.5	19.9	75.0	70.0
2023	48.7	23.7	79.1	70.6
2024	53.9	29.8	83.1	70.8
2025	50.1	26.0	78.6	71.2

From the data in this table, we can see that the GRP in Tashkent region is growing positively in 2015-2025 (from 64.8% to 50.1%, respectively). At the same time, we can also observe positive growth in industry, agriculture, fixed capital investments and services. Although the high growth of imports relative to export growth has had a significant negative impact on the foreign trade balance of our country, the overall situation can be described as positive growth in exports.

Figure 1: Cross-section of Tashkent region (for the example of industrial products).

In Tashkent region, the volume of industrial output in 2024 amounted to 139124.8 billion soums, or the industrial production index was 130.02% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year. By region, the highest share of small businesses in the production of industrial products was observed in the city of Almalyk (share in total industrial production is 31%), Chirchik (11%), Qibray (9%), Ahangaron (7%), Bekabad and Angren cities (6%), and the smallest share was observed in the cities of Parkent (1%), Chinaz (1%).

Tashkent region is one of the industrial centers of Uzbekistan, and the metallurgical industry plays an important role in the regional economy. In January-November 2024, the metallurgical industry accounted for 37.2% of the volume of industrial products produced in the region, which amounted to a total of 44,428.9 billion soums. The development of the metallurgical industry is increasing the demand for metal products used in construction, transport, energy and other sectors in the region. As of October 1, 2024, the number of operating small businesses in the Tashkent region was 36,484. Small businesses operate in various sectors of the regional economy and also have a place in areas such as the production, sale and processing of metal products. For example, a regional inter-sectoral industrial fair was organized in the "Tinchlik" small industrial zone in Yangiyul district, where small businesses in the metallurgical sector presented their products.

The volume of metal products production in the region has increased from 759 billion soums to 3.9 trillion soums over the past three years. This growth is due to the expansion of localized production, which has led to the production of import-substituting products. Small businesses are actively participating in this process, playing an important role in the production and supply of localized products.

Table 2. Volume of metal production in Tashkent region (billion soums).

Years	2021	2022	2023	2024
Production volume (billion soums)	759	1650	2830	3900
Growth rate (%)	-	217.39	372.86	513.83

As you can see, the production of metal products increased more than 5 times during 2021–2024. This growth is due to the active participation of local manufacturers, in particular small businesses.

Table 3. Growth of small businesses in Tashkent region (2020–2024)

Years	Quantity (pcs)	Growth rate
2020	25100	-
2021	28700	+14.3%
2022	31400	+9.4%
2023	34000	+8.3%
2024	36484	+7.3%

The number of small businesses is increasing every year, which means their participation in industrial sectors, including metallurgy, is increasing.

The ferrous metallurgy sector in Uzbekistan is mainly represented by the activities of Uzmetkombinat JSC (Uzbekistan Metallurgical Combine). In addition, small foundries of machine-building enterprises also play an important role in this sector. The main part of the republic's ferrous metallurgy products is produced in the Tashkent region. The leading manufacturing enterprise in the region is Uzmetkombinat JSC, located in the city of Bekabad.

Products produced by foundries belonging to the mechanical engineering industry account for only 0.1 percent of the country's total steel production. These products are mainly used for domestic needs and do not have a significant impact on national metallurgical production.

Tashkent Pipe Plant engages in the production of small diameter pipes. On this basis, Uzmetkombinat JSC is the only large enterprise in Uzbekistan and Central Asia producing steel and rolled metal products.

The enterprise has become the main pillar of the country's ferrous metallurgy industry, operating in direct contact with all sectors. According to experts, 36.1 percent of the republic's needs for rolled metal products are met by this enterprise through the processing of ferrous metal scrap. The remaining 63.9 percent is imported from countries such as Russia, Kazakhstan, and Ukraine.

Uzmetkombinat JSC, which has a monopoly status, distributes its products on the domestic market in accordance with the procedure established by the state. The majority of its products are used domestically, while the rest are exported to foreign markets.

The republic's available labor force, natural gas, electricity, and iron ore reserves, as well as the economy's growing need for metal products, create favorable conditions for the accelerated development of the ferrous metallurgy sector.

At the same time, a production process based solely on secondary raw materials does not allow for the full satisfaction of the country's needs. Analyses show that Uzbekistan has the potential to fully meet these needs through its mineral resources.

It follows that the establishment of new production facilities with a full metallurgical cycle in the country will make it possible to meet the domestic demand for rolled steel products through the use of mineral raw materials from existing deposits.

Uzbekistan has iron ore deposits, but they have not yet been fully developed. According to the Republican Geological Committee, the following iron ore deposits have been explored:

Suren-Ata(Tashkent region)

Iron(Jizzakh region)

Tebinbulok(Republic of Karakalpakstan).

Also, steel smelting slags accumulated during the activities of Uzmetkombinat JSC are an important additional raw material for ferrous metallurgy. Currently, there are more than 3 thousand tons of slag reserves, and up to 50 thousand tons of new slag are produced annually. It is possible to extract pig iron from these wastes and produce steel.

During the current technological process, the following types of waste and intermediate products are generated:

slags from the reduction furnace melt;

slags remaining from the oxygen-torch smelting process;

slags formed from the converter melt.

These slags contain more valuable metal components than the main ores, which increases their potential for processing and utilization.

An additional source of raw materials for the ferrous metallurgy of Uzbekistan is steelmaking slag generated in the activities of Uzmetkombinat JSC. More than 3 thousand tons of slag have accumulated in the waste areas of the plant, and approximately 50 thousand tons of slag are produced annually. There is a possibility of extracting pig iron from these slags, which is used in steelmaking.

Table 4. Uzmetkombinat JSC statistical data

No.	Name	Unit of measurement	2022	Plan 2023	Action 2023	% completion
1.	Current price of the product volume	billion soums	3.2486	3.0632	4.404	143.7
2.	Volume of goods at comparable price	billion soums	3.2486	3.143	3.180	101.2
3.	Capital investments	billion soums	0	299000	158116	52.82
4.	Production	billion soums	120.7	137.2	137.6	100.3

According to the statistical data presented in Table 4, the total volume of Uzmetkombinat's commodity output at current prices in 2022 was 3.2486 billion soums, which is 143.7% more than the plan of 4.404 billion soums by 2023. In relative prices, it was 3.2486 billion soums in 2022, and 3.180 billion soums in 2023, which is 101.2% more than the plan. We can see that capital investments in 2023 amounted to 158116 billion soums, which is 52.82% less than the plan. The volume of production in 2023 increased by 100.3%.

Table 5. Economic indicators of Uzmetkombinat JSC at the end of 2023

No.	Indicators	Unity	2022 in effect	2023 in effect	Completion %	Growth rate %
1.	Industrial product volume	Billions of soums	5381.0	5381.0	159.6%	107.0%
2.	Production volume	Thousand tons	1026000	1075395	104.8%	106.5%
3.	Net income	Billion soums	5299.3	7257.8	115.1%	157.6%

4.	Tannarx	Billion soums	4337.1	4942.8	113.9%	129.8%
5.	Export volume	Billion dollars	201.5	253.1	115.6%	107%
6.	Import reduction	Billion dollars	26.0	25.6	102.8%	-
7.	Investments	Billion dollars	-	93.0	63.1%	-
8.	Taxes to the state	Billion soums	568.0	794.0	145.1%	203%
9.	Net profit	Billion soums	220.3	1471.2	111.6%	67.0%
10.	Profitability ratio	%	4.1%	21.6%	-	-

Based on the table above, we can conclude that Uzmetkombinat's net income increased by 157.6% by 2023, reaching 7257.8 billion soums. The cost of production increased by 4942.8 by the current year, which is 113.9% more than planned. The volume of exports increased by 2023 compared to the previous year, reaching 253.1 billion dollars, which is 115.6% more than planned. The volume of imports decreased by 102.8% compared to planned. This is a positive indicator for the company. The higher the profitability level, the more positive it is for the company. By 2023, it is 21.6%. For reference, this indicator was 4.1% in the middle of the year.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In 2024, Uzmetkombinat JSC produced 9217.6 billion soums of industrial products in 2023, while in the first quarter of 2024 alone it amounted to 2190 billion soums. Production, including the volume of rolled products, amounted to 534 thousand tons at the end of this year, which is 31.8% less than the plan. Steel balls, while last year they amounted to 248 thousand tons, amounted to 246 thousand tons in January-December 2024. Net profit in January-September of this year amounted to 289 billion soums, which is 47% less than the plan. The profitability of the combine in January-June of this year was 7.70%, which is slightly less than half the previous year.

List of used literature:

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 166 dated 29.03.2021.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The rule of law and the protection of human interests are the key to the country's development and the well-being of the people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 48 p.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a great future with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 488 p.
4. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020. - People's Speech, January 26, 2020.
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 «On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan».
6. Azimovna, MS (2022). Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences, 1(9), 20-23.
7. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). Ways to develop marketing activities in tourist organizations. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 84-88.
8. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Issues of improving productivity competition in agriculture. Online scientific journal of innovation in social sciences.-2022.-C, 51-53.
9. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The role of marketing in increasing the economic efficiency of service enterprises.
10. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The concept of a correct marketing policy in trade and service enterprises.
11. Musayeva, S. (2022). Studying the organization of advertising activities of goods at "Samarkand tea packaging factory" JSC. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 185-192.
12. Musayeva, S. (2022). Prospects for the development of "stekloplastik" llc activity in the conditions of the market economy. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 539-546.
13. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Importance and Characteristics of Brand Choice in Services. European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 1-3.
14. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing and creative department of "STAR-SEL" LLC. Samarkand-2023
15. Musaeva Sh. A. Integrated marketing communication. Textbook. "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand -2022.

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